

7TH ESTAD

**ASSOCIAZIONE
ITALIANA DI
METALLURGIA**

**EUROPEAN STEEL TECHNOLOGY
AND APPLICATION DAYS**

VERONA, ITALY

6-9 OCTOBER 2025

Life Cycle Assessment for the electric steelmaking route in the ALCHIMIA project

F. Rossi^{*1,2}, M. Niero^{1,2}, V. Colla^{3,1}, A. Zaccara³, S. Dettori^{3,1}, L. Laid³, F. Iraldo^{2,1}

¹Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies, Sustainability and Climate Interdisciplinary Center, via Santa Cecilia 24, Pisa, Italy

² Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies, Institute of Management, Sustainability Management Lab, Piazza Martiri della Libertà 24, Pisa, Italy

³Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies, TeCIP Institute Via G. Moruzzi 1, Pisa 56124 Italy

The ALCHIMIA Project

The mission of the **ALCHIMIA** project is to provide sustainable and competitive metalworking industries in the EU with a platform to support the transition to high-quality, competitive, efficient, and green production processes with the guarantee of high-quality products in the steel-making industry

Role of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

Baseline calculation: benchmarking the environmental performances of the steelmaking processes (Electric Arc Furnaces, EAFs) located in 3 factories owned by CELSA Group, and of one cast iron production process placed in Fonderia di Torbole (FdT)

Process optimization: including environmental impact factors of the process in a multi-objective optimization model designed for one of the factories owned by CELSA Group

Comparison: comparing the environmental impacts of the process pre- and post- optimization

Methodology

1. Goal and Scope definition:

Calculating the main environmental hotspots of the steel produced in CELSA facilities. The results will represent a baseline for the optimization model.

2. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI):

The LCI consists of the collection and quantification of materials and energy consumption, the production of waste, wastewater, and emissions involved in the production of steel in CELSA factories.

3. Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA):

7 environmental impact categories are considered to describe the eco-profile of steel products.

4. Life Cycle Interpretation:

Results have been calculated and initial recommendations can be provided.

The recycling modelling approach

The “**substitution**” recycling modelling approach adopted in **ALCHIMA** assigns environmental impacts to scrap based on the embodied substances it contains (e.g., iron, copper, manganese). This method also accounts for environmental credits resulting from the recycling of output waste. Transports are also included.

This approach was selected because it enables the **optimizer** to account for the chemical composition of scraps when minimizing environmental impacts.

Life Cycle Assessment – CELSA Plants

- **Functional Unit:** producing 1 kilogram of steel, net production
- **Background Database:** Ecoinvent 3.9.1
- **LCI:** based on primary data collected by CELSA
- **Impact Assessment method:** EF3.1, recommended by the European Commission

Life Cycle Inventory flows

Inventory flows

Scraps

Vanadium

Anthracite

Water

Aluminium

Titanium

Minerals

Slags

Ferroalloys

Electricity

Gases

Dusts

The following environmental impact categories are considered as the most relevant in the metals sector (Santero and Henry, 2016):

Climate Change: this indicator measures of the effects of greenhouse gas emissions to Climate Change [$kgCO_2 eq$]

Acidification : this indicator measures the effects of acidic substances on the environment, particularly on soil and water, which can disrupt ecosystems and harm living organisms [$mol H^+ eq$]

Eutrophication (marine, freshwater, terrestrial): this indicator measures the level of nutrients released into water bodies through human activities, leading to excessive algae growth, oxygen depletion, and ecological imbalances [$kg N eq, kg P eq, mol N eq$]

Photochemical ozone formation: this indicator measures the emissions of pollutants, such as nitrogen oxides which contribute to the formation of ground-level ozone and smog, impacting human health and the environment [$kg NMVOC eq$]

Ozone depletion: Evaluates the release of substances, such as chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), that deplete the ozone layer in the stratosphere, allowing harmful ultraviolet radiation to reach the Earth's surface [$kg CFC11 eq$]

Hotspot analysis of the process stages in Celsa factory 1

Hotspot analysis of the process stages in Celsa factory 2

Hotspot analysis of the process stages in Celsa factory 3

Steel grades analysis of the process stages in Celsa factory 1

From the baseline to the optimization model

LCA is often used in decision making problems to evaluate the most environmentally sustainable choice

Possible approaches:

- **Scenario-based comparative LCA:** several scenarios are created applying reasonable variations to the amount of materials and energy used, that are set as model parameters
- **Optimized LCA:** as the number of parameters increases, the number of possible scenarios can grow significantly + predicting some parameter values can be difficult. Optimization models help address this issue by computing the mathematically optimal solution

From the baseline to the optimization model

Variables

Scraps

Vanadium

Anthracite

Aluminium

Titanium

Minerals

Ferroalloys

Electricity

Gases

Parameters

Water

Slags

Dusts

Constraints

Mass balance: input materials = output materials

Energy balance: energy inputs = energy output

Material Quality: Machine Learning correlations

Conclusions

- A LCA study is conducted to identify the main environmental hotspot of 3 steelmaking sites owned by CELSA Group.
- Steel scrap is the main environmental impact contributor for CELSA factories 1 and 2, in line with the substitution approach. LF is also impacting due to the ferroalloys.
- The differences across the 3 steel families produced by Celsa factory 1 depend on the impact category under evaluation.
- The electricity consumption in EAF is the main environmental hotspot in CELSA factory 3, due to the highly carbon intensive electricity mix – followed by iron scrap.
- Optimized LCA reduces the number of scenarios needed for evaluation, decreasing the effort required by LCA practitioners while identifying environmentally optimal material mixes

Thank you for your attention!

Dr. Federico Rossi

Sustainability and Climate Interdisciplinary Center
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies
Piazza Martiri della Libertà, 33
56127 Pisa (Italy)

federico2.rossi@santannapisa.it

This study was funded by the European Union (Project 101070046 - ALCHIMIA). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. We would like to thank all people in CELSA Group who have been involved in data collection, our former colleague Fabio Claps, and our colleagues prof. Valentina Colla, Dr. Stefano Dettori, Eng. Antonella Zaccara and Dr. Ismael Matino for their support in interpreting the data.